

INNOVATIVE COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article illustrates the using of modern information communication technologies while learning foreign languages and many teachers as well as pupils` ability to evaluate, critique, synthesize and online sources properly.*

Key words: *ICT, projector, presentation software, videos, conference tools, blogs, interactive books, interactive white boards, websites, video games.*

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается использование современных информационно-коммуникационных технологий при изучении иностранных языков, а также умение учащихся правильно оценивать, критиковать, синтезировать и онлайн-источники.*

Ключевые слова: *ИКТ, проектор, программное обеспечение для презентаций, видео, инструменты для конференций, блоги, интерактивные книги, интерактивные доски, веб-сайты, видеоигры.*

INTRODUCTION

The use of information communication technologies in teaching foreign languages, not only English but also other foreign languages, has risen sharply among the educational community. Teachers access innovations without always realizing their full implications for their students.

The use of information communication technology can enhances teaching and learning in the class atmosphere. The article presents certain features of ICT that can be used good advantages in a rich learning environment and the use of ICT in the foreign class. The article also discusses the role of the teacher in the lesson.

Technology has become an expected literacy in higher education and in our society, a universal language spoken worldwide, regardless of the profession, in classroom, technologies can be included all kind of tools from computers and internet to broadcasting technologies and telephony. Therefore under the big umbrella of ICT there are many tools that we can include such as projector, presentation software, videos, conference tools(Skype), blogs, wiki online dictionaries, interactive books, interactive whiteboard, learn foreign language websites and even video games.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

It takes a lot of time and work to master a language and there is not enough in class for that, so language educators should motivate students and teach them how to access knowledge and data from around the world in order to become independent learners. We can do that by letting them know what is available and good on the ICT. Providing online access to our teaching materials and also by sharing with students who are learning foreign language in an online environment and communicate with native speakers. ICT enables actions and interactions to be undertaken remarkably quickly, for instance messages can be sent and replies can come back in minutes or even seconds. The capacity of ICT is enormous providing access to a large amount

of information. Multimodality implies sounds, pictures and texts and it is well-known that pupils learn better foreign languages if there are more senses involved in the process of teaching.

There are also some arguments that there is growing number of students who are less motivated, less interested and less engaged in the process of learning. They also mention that the left-brain dominant students, these who work better with words, are clearly advantaged by our learning foreign languages.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Now that we know the meanings are certain characteristics with ICT, it would be highlight some of the benefits and challenges of using modern technologies in the foreign language classes. Effective modern technologies provide substantial benefits in teaching and learning foreign languages. Technologies enrich the content (photos, videos Power point) with the aid of technologies teachers provide students authentic skills and video of target culture and up to date materials in order to develop learning skills and engage students. In addition to engage student in class, the adequate use of technologies enhances classroom communication and offer students the opportunity to communicate, collaborate and interact with course material in different ways.

Although technology integration has many benefits, there are also challenges. Sometimes pupils encounter problems regarding the use of online learning software, especially the lack of the direct contact with the teacher. Pupils at the highest level have misconceptions regarding the way teachers would adapt technology in classroom. Learning language pupils in education who lack a comprehensive understanding of effective use of technology in the teaching process.

Other challenges refer to the lack of resources such as interactive whiteboards, computers connected to internet for every student, video projectors and screens. Nevertheless, technology itself is not as important as the way we exploit it. If there aren't computers for every students in the classroom, the teacher can record a video their explaining certain topics and share it with the students, who can watch it at home. Thus, we extend the learning environment outside the class and make it interactive.

CONCLUSION

No doubt interactively can also be achieved by using the blackboard, the chalk and paper. Role plays and word competitions have positive impact on pupils. We have to make sure technology remains a tool in achieving our educational purposes and does not take over the class. Human have always learned hand in hand with other humans, it has always been this way, and some way believe that technology might compromise connection created between teacher and learner, one of the best things in our educational system.

Having identified the positive and negative impacts of ICT in teaching foreign languages and also the importance of the teacher's role in educational process. In my view that we can not forget the past and the years of the research of good teaching practices developed by skilled teachers. We should carefully build and develop this ICT system based on what it already exists.

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